

SZ-HB-III-01-02 A (university) applicant looking for students (English)

Author	@Ricarda Peil ; @Julia Victoria Dinier ; @Julia Lehmler ; @Tara-Marie Endries ; @Sönke Erdmann ; @Alexander Schröter (original German version) @Jan Martin Kauter ; @Tara-Marie Endries ; @Emily Penk (English translation)
Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091552
ID	SZ-HB-III-01-02
Title	A (university) applicant looking for students
Educational area	#school #higher-education
Persona	P: Greta - Pupil https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951735
Short description	Looking for exchange with students about the entry requirements for starting a teacher training course.
Result	Search for contacts via Buddy Finder, contact and networking via chat and other components in BIRD (including contacts).
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Process "Search for Buddy(s)"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Greta is verified at BIRD• Greta has saved and shared basic data already
Components	#buddyfinder #chat #contacts
Services / tools	#video-conference

Problem scenario

Introduction

Greta Pulka is about to graduate from high school and wants to study music teaching in order to share later her passion for music. She is looking for one or more people who are already studying to become music teachers and who can give her concrete insights. Greta is particularly interested in the application and enrollment phase, but she is also eager to learn about program and the study experience itself.

Problem definition

Greta doesn't know anybody that she can ask questions about studying. She would therefore like to find someone who can provide her with information not only about her desired course of study, but also about starting her studies and applying to a university.

At the same time, Greta hopes that by interacting with students, she can better prepare for the process and requirements of the entrance exam, which is often required for music teaching programs.

Background and context

Greta creates lists to help her make a decision, and gathers as much information as possible. For Greta, it's not just about the information from the university websites. She wants to know not only how long the audition, as part of the entrance exam, takes and what it consists of, but also how it feels and what she can expect from the examiners. Personal impressions and experiences are important to her. Through the exchange with students, Greta hopes to receive more information about the course and the entry requirements.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Greta is already nervous about a possible audition, even though she has already performed in front of an audience several times. It's important to her to make the right decision when choosing a location. She doesn't want to regret her decision later .

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Greta has has problems connecting with other students because she doesn't know any of them yet. Her private music teacher has shared his experiences and those of some former students, but that's not enough for Greta. Getting information from one of the many forums or joining an unfamiliar social media group isn't Greta's first choice for establishing the connection she desires.

Activity scenario

Process "Search for Buddy(s)"

Step 1: Greta opens BIRD and navigates to the BuddyFinder

Step 2: She specifies the following attributes in the BuddyFinder search:

- City: Potsdam, Berlin, Rostock, Dresden, Halle
- University: any
- Subject: Music Teaching
- Semester: any
- Group or Individual: Individual
- Goal: Exchange (online)

At the same time, she checks the data in her BIRD profile. City, school, and interests have remained the same, to enable a better matching:

- City: Torgelow am See
- School: Schloss Torgelow
- Interests: Playing the bassoon, social media
- About me: I love Music, my favorite song is "Mozart's House" by Clean Bandit

Step 3: The BuddyFinder shows Greta several results.

Step 4: Greta looks through the results. A few of them fit reasonably well. The search didn't yield suitable offers at all requested university locations. She selects contacts from the list who share most of her attributes. These people are from different universities. She wants to contact them individually to inquire about the enrollment process at their universities.

Step 5: Greta writes a short message in the free text field with her questions and additional information about herself to create a more personal setting. She sends this message along with a contact request to the selected people via the BuddyFinder.

Step 6: They receive the contact request and read Greta's message. Some people choose to accept the contact request right away, which Greta is then notified about.

Step 7: Greta receives messages that her contact requests have been accepted and that she can now chat with her buddies..

Step 8: Greta chats with three of her buddies to get to know them better and get a sense of whether they're on the same wavelength.

Step 9: Greta arranges a video conference with two of her buddies via chat so that she can ask further questions about the entry requirements and other topics.

Step 10: Greta starts video conference via the chat in BIRD.